

Like a
PRO

Train of the Trainers

LIKE-A-PRO's Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Labs

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Train of the Trainers. LIKE-A-PRO's Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Labs

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1. Introduction

1.1 Aim of the Train of the Trainers Sessions

The aim of the three online Train the Trainers (ToT) sessions was two-fold:

- To design and deliver a series of training sessions to support the preparation of lab implementers to plan and run the LIKE-A-PRO Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Labs;
- To provide interactive, live sessions to complement and build on the living labs methodology, covering aspects from setting up the process, running the labs, refining priorities or discussion topics, to monitoring and evaluating the process and capturing lessons learned. The overarching approach is summarised in the Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Labs' Governance Framework.

1.2 Background

1.2.1 The Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Labs

The LIKE-A-PRO living labs will serve as a platform for European citizens to discuss the consumption of alternative protein (AP) products, test and provide feedback on new products developed by the project. The insights gained will then be used to collaboratively explore solutions to influence sustainable food choices. Specifically, the living labs will support the project by:

- Exploring the food environment through consumers' experiences of food consumption, focusing on accessibility, challenges, and opportunities;
- Identifying the key behavioural determinants that drive change towards healthier and more sustainable diets, and, based on the insights gained;
- Explore and advocate for governance mechanisms or solutions to create the enabling conditions in food environments that are urgently needed for the crucial dietary shifts.

1.2.2 The Consumer Choice Framework

The living labs include eight points of interaction with consumers in each of the project's pilot countries. The **Consumer Choice Framework** is used to generate insights. This methodology, consisting of four choice clusters, seeks to explore different intervention types to understand and manage consumer choice in different food environments.

- **Choice editing:** interventions that influence choice by reviewing and editing out choice options that are considered unsustainable and unhealthy;
- **Choice environment:** interventions that influence choice by creating a favourable environment for sustainable food purchase to take place, by often nudging consumers towards a desired direction;
- **Choice expansion:** interventions that can guide consumers towards the sustainable and healthier options by increasing the number of the options / products available, while keeping other options open also;
- **Beyond choice:** interventions that are more systemic in nature and go beyond the specific point and time of food purchase, but still impact consumer choice e.g., education campaigning.

1.3 Methodology

The design and facilitation of the three training sessions were carried out using the subsequent methodology.

1.3.1 Approach, Structure & Topics

The overarching idea was to develop a training programme with an interactive, capacity-building approach. In order to create something practical and of lasting value to the project partners, the design of the sessions incorporated key principles such as:

- Ensuring the alignment of the framework with practical steps by basing the content on existing or developing project resources related to the design and implementation of the Living Labs Governance Framework and PRES;
- Providing a platform for partners to exchange good practice and ideas with each other, recognising the diverse and varied experiences within the group (i.e., promoting peer learning);
- Focusing each session content on practical aspects relevant to local partners, ensuring alignment with the tasks they would undertake when setting up and running living labs: this includes recruitment and engagement of participants, design and implementation of the living labs, and follow-up activities after the labs;
- Balancing information sharing/presentations, whole group discussions/activities and small group work to optimise engagement, retain key information and enhance capacity for the activities ahead.

The sessions were structured as a 3-part series of two-hours online interactive exchanges, where each training session covered a topic of relevance to the LIKE-A-PRO living labs' implementers, namely:

- Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy (PRES);
- Planning and Running a Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Lab;
- Guidelines, Data Collection and Transcription, Feedback & Long-term Engagement.

1.3.2 Facilitation Methods

A variety of facilitation methods were used throughout the three online sessions to increase interactivity and provide practical guidance and insights for partners in organising a living labs event. These methods included presentations, icebreakers, Q&A sessions, whole group brainstorming, whole group and small group discussions, small group activities such as completing templates tailored to local contexts, and feedback collection.

1.3.3 Online Environment & Participants

The online training sessions were conducted using the ZOOM video call platform. Visual support was provided through MIRO boards which were used to present information and allow participants to contribute to plenary and breakout group activities. This report includes key highlights and the results from the exchanges throughout the different sessions. The full and detailed overview of the results has been archived and is available to partners for their ongoing work.

A registration link was set up for each session to determine the number of participants and to pre-assign individuals to breakout groups. Although attendance of at least one representative from each local partner was encouraged, with no limit on attendance, sessions were recorded for those unable to attend and for future reference to ensure that partners could make use of the information gathered. The recordings are available within the project files for partners to review as required.

The sessions had respectively:

- 25 participants in Session 1;
- 19 in Session 2; and
- 21 for Session 3, as indicated by the online registrations.

A comprehensive list of participants is provided in Appendix 1.

Figure 1: Screenshot of the group during one of the online training sessions.

1.3.4 Organising Partners' Roles

CSCP collaborated with WWM to create the sessions. The specific roles carried out by each partner are outlined in the table below.

Table 1: Roles and responsibilities of organising partners.

Organisation	Role in training sessions
CSCP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall design of the 3-session series • Overall facilitation of the 3 sessions • Facilitation of small groups' discussions • Design of training materials (e.g., agendas, Miro boards and facilitation notes) • Development of content for some presentations/activities (e.g., overview of elements of laboratory methods, digital tools) • Coordination of participants (registration and breakout planning) • Technical support
WWM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content development for some presentations/activities (e.g., overview of PRES strategy) • Facilitation and moderation of small groups' discussions

1.3.5 Overview of the Sessions

The training sessions took place on the dates listed below:

Table 2. The 3 ToTs in a nutshell.

Date	Session Topic
Monday, 13th November 2023, 10:00 to 12:30h.	The Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy (PRES)
Monday, 27th November 2023, 11:00 to 13:00h.	Planning and Running a Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Lab Meeting / Interaction Point
Monday, 11th December 2023, 10:30 to 12:30h.	Guidelines, Data Collection and Transcription, Feedback & Long-term Engagement

The next parts of this report provide an overview of each session: the specific aims, the agenda, and the outputs produced.

2. Session 1: The Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy (PRES)

2.1 Aim & Agenda

The first training session focused on the living labs PRES and aimed:

- to provide an overview of the information and tools and to increase the capacity of local LIKE-A-PRO lab partners to recruit and maintain the interest of lab participants throughout the living labs journey;
- to further explore the characteristics of lab participants, including their motivations for participating and engaging with the topic;
- to look at the different forms and communication channels that can be used to recruit and engage participants, including the different organisations and other external project partners (i.e., multipliers) that can support this process.

The ultimate aim was to ensure the recruitment of a diverse range of people from different social and demographic groups to make the project outputs broadly representative.

This session emphasized crucial content derived from both the Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy (PRES). Below the agenda of this training session is provided.

Table 3. Agenda of 1st ToT session.

Training Session 1: The Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy (PRES) Monday 13th November: 10:00 - 12:30 (CET)		
Time	Session	Activity
10:30-10:40	Welcome and Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome • Objectives of the day • Agenda overview
10:40-11:10	The LIKE a PRO PRES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short presentation on the key components of the strategy: • The WHO [map participants and identify multipliers] • The HOW [identify motivations] • The AFTER [collect messaging and outreach activities]

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Q&A
11:00-12:10	Implementing the PRES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The group split into 3 different small groups (mixing pilot countries) to conduct an interactive exercise on Miro focusing on the three different types of living lab settings: Find and map your living labs participants Identify multipliers Identify motivations and set up messages Communication channels and outreach activities
12:10-12:25	Reporting back from the working session	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants shared insights from the groups' discussions
12:25-12:30	Wrap up and closing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Next steps in preparation of Session 2 Closing

The following figures provide an overview of the Miro boards used to guide the presentation of the PRES (i.e., the WHO, the HOW and the AFTER). Specifically, the first relates to the criteria and aspects to be considered when mapping key participants for each lab meeting (i.e., lab participants characteristics). While the second Miro board presents the meaning behind the word "multipliers" and explains the links between possible multipliers and lab participants' engagement within the LIKE-A-PRO project context and key objectives.

Figure 2. Miro boards template on mapping participants.

The Miro board (Figure 4) provided further guidance on the key motivations, possible incentives, and related messaging approaches to be used to maximise outreach activities in relation to the living labs. A full overview of the content can be found in the PRES document.

2.2 Outputs

Using the information and knowledge presented in the above-mentioned introductory Miro boards, lab implementers were then divided into three working groups to share and try out for themselves the mapping of possible participants, including the elaboration of key motivations and messages linked to respective outreach activities and tools. During the session, lab implementers were also asked to identify multipliers who could support the recruitment of identified lab participants. The screenshots below provide an overview of the exercise, which was conducted for different types of living labs, namely: conventional exchanges, product feedback and point-of-sale¹.

Table 4 and Table 5 provide a detailed overview (transcribed) of the content from these Miro boards (Figure 7-9).

Figure 5. Living Lab type: Conventional Exchange.

Figure 6. Living Lab type: Product Feedback.

¹ After the first ToT, the living lab typology was subject of a slight change. The product feedback lab type was merged with the other ones, and the project team decided to continue with two lab types only: conventional exchanges and interaction at the point of sale.

Figure 7. Living Lab type: Point-of-Sale Lab.

Table 4. Synthesized inputs to relevant target groups of the living labs ToT session 1.

Participants of the living labs	
Target Group Type	Examples given by workshop participants
Age Groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> not underaged young adults middle aged people (as APs are new topic to them) elderly people / retired people
Social Groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> students different education levels (young) families vulnerable groups (e.g., homeless) food communities
Other demographics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> cities vs. rural areas (factor accessibility) number of household members type of household (e.g., couple, family, flatshare) different employment types canteen staff different genders → esp. women (usually making food decisions in households)
Food preferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> vegans, vegetarians, flexitarians people favouring local food meat lovers
Other types	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> customers of bazaars local producers different interest in sustainability varying willingness to spend

Table 5. Synthesized inputs to motivations and activities ToT session 1.

Motivation	Outreach activities/ Tools	Multipliers
Perceived health benefits		
one of the strongest motivators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> frame the invitation to the living labs broader (e.g., “Food development” instead of “Alternative Proteins”) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> celebrities as campaign face
A sense of (wider) community		
people want to be heard, also from specific communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> invite families and serve dinner with APs disseminate invitations in social media (e.g., Facebook) community groups advertise local distribute posters and flyers at local shops collaborate with regional partners use direct personal contact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> families social media community groups local shops local radio/ newspaper regional companies
social norms		
Curiosity and feeling adventurous		
adventure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> combine yoga sessions/ music sessions with food offers sending invitations to/ attending association meetings people are already going to gamification be visual and interactive sending LIKE-A-PRO-products as try-out-gifts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> local shops existing social media channels
follow new trends		
curiosity for new products/ Aps as innovations		
Economic		
improved reputation for supermarkets/ restaurants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> small gifts (e.g., free foods, discounts) offering gift basket with available APs products 	
consider motivations of partners to function as a living lab location (e.g., universities, supermarkets)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> consider sponsors for sampling 	
increased visibility		
pricing/budget		
Product development		
help to integrate more APs in menus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> sending LIKE A PRO products as try-out-gifts 	
discussing the future of food production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> co-creation 	

Overall		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> personal messages and tailored to each group write emails to universities using influencers esp. to reach younger generations use existing social media channels connect with multipliers so that they aid the participants recruitment conduct in-person workshops via the multipliers continuous engagement in outreach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> municipalities/ NGOs (provide legitimacy) university canteens work canteens food courts existing social media channels consumer database (fast-food-) restaurants

3. Session 2: Planning and Running a Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Lab Meeting

3.1 Aim & Agenda

The 2nd ToT session concentrated on the planning and implementation of impactful living labs' events, with a focus on making them as engaging and effective as possible with regards to the results that need to be generated. The session aimed to provide lab implementers with an overview:

- of principles and tips for making the lab meetings interactive, engaging and purposeful;
- facilitation techniques to generate the necessary content / results;
- of tips and hints regarding organisational logistics (venue and timing) that allows for a diverse and inclusive participant sample.

These aims were translated into the below provided agenda:

Table 6. Agenda of 2nd ToT session.

Training Session 2: Planning and Running a LIKE-A-PRO Living Lab Monday 27th November: 11-13:00 (CET)		
Time	Session	Activity
11:00 - 11:05	Welcome and Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome Objectives of the day Agenda overview
11:05 - 11:30	Planning living lab meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Short presentation on the key aspects to start designing your living lab meeting focusing on two main types of living labs: Conventional exchanges/ co-creation Point-of-Sale meeting Q&A
11:30 - 12:55	How to plan a living lab meeting? Let's design an agenda together!	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The group split into 2 different small groups to conduct an interactive exercise on MIRO discussing key aspects to consider: The WHY [defining the scope & objectives of your lab meeting] The WHEN & WHERE [Locations, logistics and timing] The HOW [qualitative facilitation methods/tools]

12:55 -13:00	Wrap up and closing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Next steps in preparation of Session 3 • Closing
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The session began with an overview of the overall approach of the LIKE-A-PRO living labs, including the main methodology to be used and the objectives to guide the different lab iterations as described in **Section 1.2.1 and 1.2.2.**

Following, through the Miro boards (shown below) a detailed overview of the three main components to be considered when planning and implementing a lab meeting were provided, namely:

- The WHY: defining the scope and objectives of the lab meeting
- The WHEN & WHERE: locations, logistics and timing
- The HOW: creating an interactive meeting example including facilitation tools.

A full overview of the content can be found in the Governance Framework and the PRES.

The WHY: Defining the scope & objectives of your CILL meeting

The LIKE A PRO living labs act as a **forum to exchange, discuss and co-create** with European citizens / consumers on a range of topics related to their food choices and the way how these are made in food environments.

With regards to **food environments**, the LIKE A PRO living labs will seek to be present and work with the most **frequent points of sale where consumers make their food choices**. For example, supermarkets, restaurants, canteens (universities, public institutions), food and farmers markets and similar.

★ Start thinking about the key scope and objectives of the event, within your organization start defining the overarching goal of the meeting and develop a list of specific objectives

★ Reach out and exchange with the CSCP as well as to others local lab implementers (if needed) to brainstorm together with respect to the aims and focus of the FE CILL meeting that you are planning

Before start planning any FE CILL meeting, it is important to ask yourself: what do I want to achieve with this meeting? What are my key objectives?

Aim	Outcome
To introduce the Like a PRO project to citizens	The participants know what the Like a PRO project is about
Set up the context and inform participants about the different possibilities for collaboration and engagement throughout the entire living labs journey and beyond in other project activities	Participants understand the project's activities and final aim
To explore and better understand citizens' knowledge and consumption habits of alternative proteins and their related food environments	Participants gathered a better understanding of the type of alternative proteins the Like a PRO project is focusing on
To exchange and get a first feeling about Europeans' attitudes, preferences as well as readiness to integrate alternative proteins in their dietary patterns	Participants have understood and discussed possibilities to switch to a diet including alternative proteins

💡 Remember to contextualize the co-creation activities and questions to your local setting!

Figure 8. Miro board on the WHY (scope and objectives) of a living lab.

Figure 9. Miro board on the WHEN & WHERE, referring to two type of living lab formats.

Figure 10. Miro board on the HOW: running an interactive and impactful lab meeting.

3.2 Outputs

The introductory part was followed by a practical exercise that immersed participants in the key aspects of designing a comprehensive lab session agenda. Specifically, partners were divided into two working groups

to undertake an interactive exercise focusing on two categories of the Consumer Choice Framework, namely Choice Expansion (Figure 11) and Choice Environment (Figure 12).

Figure 11. Choice Expansion Lab Iteration.

This interactive component provided a tangible platform for participants to experiment with different elements, ensuring a holistic understanding of how to structure a living lab meeting for optimal engagement. This exercise not only provided lab implementers theoretical concepts, but also in a practical manner some more insights into the dynamic interplay of elements that contribute to the overall success of a living lab. In addition, lab implementers spent time refining and contextualising the goals and purpose of the lab meeting. The process involved a thoughtful examination of how the goals of the meeting aligned with the overarching goals of the living labs initiative within the LIKE-A-PRO project. By ensuring alignment, lab implementers aimed to create a

cohesive framework that would maximise the potential for generating meaningful outcomes and insights. The key outcomes and insights resulting from the exercise have been summarised in the Table 7 and Table 8.

Figure 12. Choice Environment Lab Iteration.

Table 7. Summary of the input developed during the exercise on the Conventional Exchange lab type.

Conventional Exchange	
Choice Expansion	Choice Environment
The WHY	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • definition of APs by consumers (e.g., what they consider as APs) • are APs already consumed in target group (If so, why/ not?) • associations of highly-processed food & in connection to APs • fair price estimations for APs • attitude towards traditional proteins sources • perceived health and nutrition aspects and their influence on consumption choices • are cooks willing to use APs? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • are AP products related to ultra-processed food? • how do claims on packaging influence non-consumers of APs? • perception of reducing portion sizes
The WHEN	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lunch or dinner time 	
The WHERE	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • university canteens, classes • student Hotel/ apartments • restaurant • cafeteria • community centres with/ without food • municipality building • multifunctional cultural spaces • work places • collaboration with local associations (DIY, hunting etc.) • day-care organisation • children's activity park to engage with parents • partnering with existing living labs • online interviews (more convenient) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • inviting restaurant owners, chefs to the living labs in their role as consumers
The HOW	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • focus groups • tasting/ cooking workshop • round table discussion with ca 30 people accompanied by facilitator • showing participants APs • presenting raw materials (where AP come from) vs. final product • introduction of APs in general with (visual) presentation of them • expert from related field to share insights • co-creating/ validating marketing value propositions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • no tasting • show how to cook APs (co-creative cooking workshop) • visual facilitations (e.g., pictures to enhance understanding) • showing raw materials first (where AP come from) then final product • discussion of different menus and its influence

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • holding everything constant between countries (same packaging, definitions etc.) • how to deal with different opinions regarding APs 	
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Table 8. Summary of the input developed during the exercise focusing on the Point-of-Sale lab type.

Point-of-Sale	
Choice Expansion	Choice Environment
The WHY	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • definition of APs by consumers • associations of highly-processed food & in connection to APs (negative connotation?) • would consumers purchase more if a wider variety APs types were available? • what cooking format of AP is preferred? • what influences consumers choices at the point of sale (PoS)? • how does the source of APs affect willingness to choose it? • understanding “competition” between existing products and new ones • what information do consumers want on packaging? On which information do they look? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • status quo: Are there any AP products already available? variety? quality? etc.
The WHEN	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • after working hours for working population • during working hours (e.g., for elderly/ incapacitated/ stay-at-home parents) • schedule most convenient time for all 	
The WHERE	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • university (canteens) or other education places • work canteen • cafeteria • farmers market • supermarkets (not most expansive one, not peak hours) • butcher vs. organic shops (2 opposite perspectives) • fast-food-restaurants • soup-kitchens • community-centre (serving food at low price) • comfortable environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • university canteens or other education places • restaurant offering innovative/ veggie dishes • conventional supermarket vs. specialized • supermarkets general vs. separate shelf for AP products in supermarkets
The HOW	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • key questions that can be asked in less than 15 min • real-life scenarios with AP • have physical products/ printed photos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • no tasting • show different AP labels and discuss • discuss different orders of dishes on menu & its influence

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • taste tests • handing out samples 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • active listening • focus groups • interviews
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4. Session 3: Guidelines, Data Collection and Transcription, Feedback & Long-term Engagement

4.1 Aim & Agenda

The aim of the 3rd and final ToT training session was to:

- gather lab implementers feedback and insights with regards to the plans for designing the specific lab iterations guidelines which will provide a more detailed overview of how to organise and conduct lab meetings and/or interaction points with consumers;
- exchange and agree with lab implementers on how to collect, transcribe as well as report demographic data as well as the results from the exchanges with consumers;
- share best practices for sustaining consumers' engagement and interest from one lab meeting to the other.

The agenda for this session is provided below:

Table 9. Agenda of the 3rd ToT session.

Training Session 3: Guidelines, Data Collection and Transcription, Feedback & Long-term Engagement Monday 11th December: 10:30-12:30 (CET)		
Time	Session	Activity
10:30 – 10:35	Welcome and Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome • Objectives of the day • Agenda overview
10:35 - 11:30	Plenary Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lab iterations guideline • How to structure input/data • Socio-demographic data collection • Living lab meetings report and transcription templates • Sharing insights externally & internally
12:25 -12:30	Wrap up and closing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closing

4.2 Outputs

As with the other ToT sessions, this one began with a brief introduction providing an overview of the agenda and objectives of the meeting. Different from the other sessions, in this one, key topical agenda points were followed by an exchange after a short introduction. For example, after a short introduction of an example of a guideline (i.e., the guideline of lab iteration 1 on choice editing), lab implementers exchanged on it and shared their feedback on how to further refine and improve the guideline in a manner that is more helpful to them. Similarly, participants discussed and explored different methods for collecting, organising and analysing the data stemming from the lab iterations to draw meaningful results. In addition, recognising the importance of socio-demographic data, participants engaged in a focused discussion on ethical and effective

methods for collecting this information in a living lab setting. Finally, lab implementers provided their feedback on the reporting and transcription templates which are planned to be utilised to collect the data and information originating from the lab meetings, after an introduction of the former. The focus was on ensuring consistency and clarity in communicating the results and discussions with lab participants. **Tables 18-20** summarise these exchanges.

Figure 13. Lab Iterations Guideline.

Table 10. Synthesized feedback to the lab iteration guidelines, general report and transcription.

Lab iteration guidelines	General Report	Transcription Templates
What do you think is helpful?		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> overview detailed plan for sessions for each country (potential adjustment due to local situation) informed consent before session suggested agenda/ timeline same questions for all stakeholder across countries diverse participants structuring research questions leads to mire comparable data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> was used in other project & worked nicely 	
What is not helpful?		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> concerned about duration of one hour for point-of-sale (people during shopping won't have time) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> how to ask about disability? Only ask questions only if they are useful and relevant 	
What do you think is missing?		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • more information on cluster mechanisms/ definition of choice editing • more information on content of longer sessions • guidelines for collaborating with point-of-sale-partners • clarification on how to present APs to consumers • more information on exact input in the living labs • which aspects should be prioritized when collecting data • data analysing procedure 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the excel might be too open to interpretation
Other ideas and ways you would like to help		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When involving a research student/intern, is it possible for them to use the data for their study/graduation project? • APs overview • role of culture /advertisement/ education on cluster mechanisms • point-of-sale at university canteens possible with majority being students? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • structured feedback makes report writing easier • clear structure where to place the data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • coding tree • point-of-sale: might trace data back to the SED data? • at the beginning of a living lab meeting / interaction point: short questionnaire with informed consent

As depicted in the following **Table 11**, feedback on how to structure the data collected was done using the COM-B model, the Consumer Choice Framework or other ideas provided by the partners.

Table 11. Gathered ideas on how to bring together collected data/input.

COM-B Model	Consumer Choice Framework	Other ideas
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • unclarity about difference between capabilities and opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • all COM-B components are also part of the Consumer Choice Framework according to the guidelines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • how to merge feedback from different countries → help from WP1 deliverables
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • important to have example questions that focus on the model 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • varying settings might influence outcomes of the different living labs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • meta-Review on the model and alternative proteins in WP1 deliverable 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • coding tree • suggestion (from WP2/3) to focus on the type of AP and products

With regard to the collection and analysis of socio-demographic data, ideas were gathered in relation to a specific type of living labs' meeting, as the nature and intrinsic characteristics of this type of meeting significantly alter the way in which this type of data can be collected.

Table 12. Collected input on socio-demographic data and consent form.

Conventional exchanges/ co-creation workshops	Point-of-Sale Living Labs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> split reasons for why collecting results for different target groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> easy, forward consent form (Note book or 1 paper)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> signed consent is a must 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> consent form might reduce willingness to participate in conversation VS. without it, they might feel uncomfortable
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> collecting socio-demographic and consent should be mandatory for the questionnaire afterwards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> verbal or printed/digital informed consent?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> less about participants signing the form, more about who is responsible for the data
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> work with business cards/ QR codes/ numbers for identifying the person
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> using recorder → consent is a must (voice considered as personal information)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> collecting personal or complete anonymous data? anonymity = person can't be traced back in any way

In addition, lab implementers provided valuable input on how to effectively share the learning from the lab meetings both externally with lab participants and internally across the 11 living labs within the project for improvement purposes. Externally, partners emphasised the importance of active engagement with lab participants. Recommendations included the use of emails to share concise summaries of activities and outcomes, demonstrating the tangible impact of participants' involvement. In addition, the creation of social media groups, such as on Facebook, was suggested as a means of encouraging ongoing engagement. However, it was recognised that sustaining this engagement depends on the motivation of participants and their openness to invitations, so ongoing iterations are more likely to attract a certain type of engaged participant. Internally, strategies for effective knowledge management within the project were outlined. Suggestions included the adoption of a quick bullet point format to document learnings about successes and challenges after each iteration. The use of Teams and its chat function was identified as a practical platform for internal communication and collaboration.

5. Conclusions

This report serves as a comprehensive overview of the methodology used in structuring and conducting the LIKE-A-PRO ToT sessions as well as highlighting the key results from each session. Detailed documentation has been carefully compiled and is available to all local partners. This documentation is intended to serve as a valuable reference during the development and implementation of the LIKE-A-PRO living labs in the respective pilot countries. The interactive and collaborative approach adopted has been designed to foster a culture of shared learning and capacity building among the project partners (lab implementers), in line with the overall objective of creating a network of informed partners who can collectively contribute to the success and sustainability of the LIKE-A-PRO living labs. Importantly, the knowledge and input generated during the three ToT sessions should not be seen as static, but rather as part of an ongoing process, with ongoing sharing and capacity building initiatives planned as the project progresses.

Appendix 1: Participant lists

Training session 1 participants list (from registration form)			
No.	Name	Organisation	Country
1	Francesca Grossi	Facilitator (CSCP)	Germany
2	Rosa Strube	Facilitator (CSCP)	Germany
3	Arlind Xhelilli	Facilitator (CSCP)	Germany
4	Floor Severens	Facilitator (WZV)	Netherlands
5	Lieske van der Waals	Facilitator (WZV)	Netherlands
6	Nina de Graaf	Facilitator (WZV)	Netherlands
7	Athanasios Krystallis	ACG-RC	Greece
8	Polymeros Chrysochou	ACG-RC	Greece
9	Elena Romero Melgosa	CTIC-CITA	Spain
10	Irene González	CTIC-CITA	Spain
11	Otso Sillanaukee	Demos	Finland
12	Isabel Boerdam	WWM	Netherlands
13	Britt Sandvad	FOODCLUSTER	Denmark
14	Louise Johnson	FOODCLUSTER	Denmark
15	Marina Baliac	IT	Slovenia
16	Sasa Straus	ITC	Slovenia
17	Bjørn Tore Nystrand	Møreforsking	Norway
18	Lisa Midtbø	Møreforsking	Norway
19	Hanna Zaleśkiewicz	SWPS	Poland
20	Jowita Misiakowska	SWPS	Poland
21	Ewa Kullis	SWPS	Poland
22	Jowita Misakowska	SWPS	Poland
23	Antonella Samoggia	UNIBO	Italy
24	Giulia Rossi	UNIBO	Italy
25	Menevis Uzbay Pirilli	ZEYTINCE	Turkey
26	Pinar Börü	ZEYTINCE	Turkey

Training session 2 participants list (from registration form)			
No.	Name	Organisation	Country
1	Francesca Grossi	Facilitator (CSCP)	Germany
2	Rosa Strube	Facilitator (CSCP)	Germany
3	Floor Severens	WZV	Netherlands
4	Lieske van der Waals	WZV	Netherlands
5	Polymeros Chrysochou	ACG-RC	Greece
6	Irene González	CTIC-CITA	Spain
7	Otso Sillanaukee	DEMOS	Finland
8	Britt Sandvad	FOODCLUSTER	Denmark
9	Louise Johnson	FOODCLUSTER	Denmark
10	Conny Hanhøj	FOODCLUSTER	Denmark
11	Marina Baliac	ITC	Slovenia

12	Sasa Straus	ITC	Slovenia
13	Bjørn Tore Nystrand	Møreforsking	Norway
14	Lisa Midtbø	Møreforsking	Norway
15	Anna Kornafel	SWPS	Poland
16	Zofia Szczuka	SWPS	Poland
17	Antonella Samoggia	UNIBO	Italy
18	Guilia Rossi	UNIBO	Italy
19	Pinar Börü	ZEYTINCE	Turkey
20	Menevis Uzbay Orililli	ZEYTINCE	Turkey
21	Onur Özden	ZEYTINCE	Turkey

Training session 3 participants list (from registration form)			
No.	Name	Organisation	Country
1	Francesca Grossi	Facilitator (CSCP)	Germany
2	Rosa Strube	Facilitator (CSCP)	Germany
3	Arlind Xhelilli	Facilitator (CSCP)	Germany
4	Lisa Mai	Facilitator (CSCP)	Germany
5	Floor Severens	WZV	Netherlands
6	Lieske van der Waals	WZV	Netherlands
7	Toula Perrea	ACG-RC	Greece
8	Irene González	CTIC-CITA	Spain
9	Otso Sillanaukee	DEMOS	Finland
10	Britt Sandvad	FOODCLUSTER	Denmark
11	Louise Johnson	FOODCLUSTER	Denmark
12	Conny Hanhøj	FOODCLUSTER	Denmark
13	Lore Bonneux	PROEF	Belgium
14	Marina Baliac	ITC	Slovenia
15	Sasa Straus	ITC	Slovenia
16	Bjørn Tore Nystrand	Møreforsking	Norway
17	Hanna Zaleśkiewicz	SWPS	Poland
18	Guilia Rossi	UNIBO	Italy
19	Pinar Börü	ZEYTINCE	Turkey
20	Menevis Uzbay Orililli	ZEYTINCE	Turkey